

Salting out and interfacial tensions of methane in electrolyte solutions as described by the Madrid-2019 force field

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Abstract

The solubility of methane in water decreases when a small amount of salt is present. This is usually denoted as the salting out effect (i.e, the methane is expelled from the solution when it contains small amounts of salt). The effect is important, for instance the solubility is reduced by a factor of three in a 4 molal (mol/kg) NaCl solution. Some years ago we showed that the salting out effect of methane in water can be described qualitatively by molecular models using computer simulations. However the salting out effect was overestimated. In fact, it was found that the solubility of methane was reduced by a factor of eight. This points out to limitations of the force field used. In this work we have carried out direct coexistence simulations to describe the salting out effect of methane in water using a recently proposed force field (denoted as Madrid-2019) based on the use of scaled charges for the ions and the TIP4P/2005 force field for water. For NaCl the results of the Madrid-2019 force field improve significantly the description of the salting out of methane. For other salts the results are quite reasonable. Thus the reduction of charge of the ions seems also to be able to improve the description of the salting out effect of methane in water. Besides we shall show that the water-salt-methane solution exhibits an increased interfacial tension as compared to that of pure water. It is well known that electrolytes tend to increase the interfacial free energy of liquid water, and it seems to be also the case when methane is present in the solution.

I. INTRODUCTION

The solubility of a gas in water can be enhanced (salting in) or reduced (salting out) by the presence of a certain solute. Electrolyte solutions (and in particular those formed by NaCl and water) are of high practical interest.¹⁻⁸ In general, the solubility of gases in water decreases by the addition of salt (i.e salting out). The effect is important and well known from an experimental point of view. Methane is a gas of considerable interest. For instance, methane hydrates are formed in the proximity of the coast.⁹ Thus, methane hydrates are often found in solutions containing NaCl and, therefore, the impact of salt in the solubility of methane is also of high practical interest.

The problem of the salting out has been addressed from a theoretical perspective by Graziano.¹⁰ Computer simulations could be useful to understand and predict this effect. To study the salting out of methane in water, a good force field for methane in water (in the absence of salt) is first required. It can be stated that at this point we have reasonable force fields for both molecules. Methane can be described reasonably well by a LJ site^{11,12}, and water by the TIP4P/2005 model¹³. Of course having a good force field for pure methane and water fluids does not guarantee that the solubility of methane in water is accurately predicted. If one wants to reproduce the experimental values of the solubility, one also needs to tailor the cross methane-water interactions. In fact we have shown in the past^{14,15} that to predict accurate values of the chemical potential and the solubility of methane the strength of the methane-water interaction must be increased by approximately a seven per cent.¹⁴ The enhancement seems an effective way of introducing the polarization undergone by the molecule of methane when solvated by water. Interestingly a similar increase of the strength of the interaction between protein atoms and water (as described by the TIP4P/2005 model) has dramatically improved the description of intrinsically disordered proteins in water as shown by Best et al.¹⁶.

Once the interactions in the binary methane/water system are satisfactorily described, a good force field for the ions in water is needed to study salting out effects. A quick search in the literature brings a number of force fields names,¹⁷⁻⁴⁴ like AMBER, GROMOS, CHARMM and OPLS-AA, used by a large scientific community (see Ref 45-47 for details on the parameters of these force fields). However, in the recent years a serious problem with these force fields has emerged. For most of them NaCl spontaneously precipitates even at

concentrations as low as 1.5 m or 2 m ⁴⁵ (the solubility limit of NaCl in water is of about 6.1 m). Since spontaneous precipitation of salt in water occurs for high supersaturations (i.e., when the concentration is about five times higher than the solubility),^{48,49} this indicates that the solubility of these force fields is well below 0.5 m . For instance, for the OPLS model of NaCl in combination with the SPC/E water⁵⁰ model, the solubility was found to be as small as 0.02 m .⁵¹ Thus, the results obtained with these force fields will not be too useful as the ions will cluster in water in an artificial way. Reports on ion-clustering were already documented in many papers in the last 20 years. In fact, in simulations the precipitation of NaCl,^{29,52-55} KCl,^{31,56} CaCl₂,⁵⁷ Na₂SO₄,⁵⁸ , Li₂SO₄⁵⁹ and KCl,^{31,56} CaCl₂,⁵⁷ at concentrations below the solubility limit has been found. It is clear that a good force field for ions in water should have reasonable values of the solubility. In the last years, thanks to the works of Smith, Nezbeda and coworkers^{17,60-62}, Panagiotopoulos and coworkers⁶³⁻⁶⁶ and also of ourselves^{67,68} it has become clear that, when modelling salts in water, solubility matters. Some other widely used force fields have also low values of the solubility of NaCl in water as it is the case for the Smith-Dang model²³ (SD) with a solubility around 0.6 m and that of Joung and Cheatham⁶⁹ (JC) with a solubility around 3.7 m ^{42,65,68} (using the SPC/E model for water⁵⁰).

In the last years a recent debate is taking place about the values of the charges to be used when describing the ions in water solutions. Should one accept the integer value, i.e ± 1 (in electron units) or should one use a scaled value of the charge, i.e 0.70 or 0.85? The origin of this discussion is as follows. In 2012 Yethiraj and coworkers⁷⁰ showed that none of the many models tested (both polarizable and non-polarizable) could reproduce the experimentally observed trends for the concentration dependence of the diffusion coefficient of water in several electrolyte solutions indicating that probably the ion-water interaction was too strong. Then Kann and Skinner⁷¹ followed a suggestion of Leontyev and Stuchebrukhov⁷²⁻⁷⁷ and described electrolytes in water using scaled charges. The idea of using scaled charges for ions in water is usually denoted as the electronic continuum correction (ECC), It can also be regarded as a consequence of the fact that the potential energy and the dipole moment surfaces may need different parameters to be described by empirical force fields^{78,79}. Soon, other groups as that of Jungwirth,^{57,80,81} Barbosa,⁸² and Wang^{83,84} joined this idea. We recently proposed a force field for NaCl in water that uses scaled charges for the ionic components, and extended the concept to other electrolytes in 2019 proposing the so called

Madrid-2019^{85,86} force field for electrolytes in water. Densities and transport properties seems to be better described by the use of scaled charges^{86,87}. The justification behind this approach is to assume that there is a certain transfer of charge from the water molecules in the hydration layer to the ions.

In this work we intend to address the problem of the salting out of methane in water following up our previous work on this problem¹⁵ with two goals in mind. The first one is to test if the Madrid-2019 force field can describe the corresponding experimental results. The second one is to throw light on a more fundamental question in the modelling of ions in water: are scaled charges superior when describing the salting out effects than models that use unit charges? Thus our study aims to describe a system of high interest and also to bring to the community a problem that can be very useful to improve our understanding of our success/limitations in the modelling of ions in water.

II. MODEL

In this work we shall evaluate the solubility of methane in aqueous electrolyte solutions of different salts. In particular we shall consider the following salts: NaCl, KCl, MgCl₂, CaCl₂, Na₂SO₄, K₂SO₄, and MgSO₄. We shall use a rigid non-polarizable force field. The pairwise interaction potential between atoms is given by an electrostatic (coulombic) contribution and a van der Waals interaction represented by the LJ potential:

$$u(r_{ij}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{q_i q_j}{r_{ij}} + 4\epsilon_{ij} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right], \quad (1)$$

where, q_i is the ionic charge, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, ϵ_{ij} the well depth energy of the LJ potential, and σ_{ij} the LJ diameter.

To describe water we shall use the TIP4P/2005 model developed by Abascal and Vega¹³ which is a reliable model of water⁸⁸⁻⁹¹. This model is based on the TIP4P water proposed by Jorgensen *et al.*⁹² as TIP4P like models give good predictions for the melting point and the phase diagram of water⁹³⁻⁹⁶. TIP4P/2005 water has four atoms, two hydrogen with charge q_H , one oxygen which is a LJ site and a site M, near the oxygen atom on the symmetric axis, without mass but with charge q_M . The TIP4P/2005 water geometry is given by the next parameters: oxygen-hydrogen distance, $d_{OH}=0.9572$ Å, oxygen-M distance, $d_{OM}=0.1546$ Å and angle H-O-H=104.52°. Methane will be described by a single Lennard Jones (LJ)

site (without partial charge) with the parameters proposed by Guillot and Guissani¹¹ and Paschek¹². The Lennard Jones parameters of the interaction between water and methane are obtained from the following expression:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{\sigma_i + \sigma_j}{2} \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon_{ij} = \chi \sqrt{\epsilon_i \cdot \epsilon_j} \quad (3)$$

When $\chi = 1$ one recovers the so called Lorentz-Berthelot (LB) rules. In previous work we have shown that to describe correctly the solubility of methane in water it is necessary to introduce deviations from the energetic LB combining rule. For this reason we shall use the value $\chi = 1.07$ for the interaction between methane in water as described in our previous work¹⁴. The parameters obtained in this way are similar to the ones proposed by Ashbaugh *et al.*⁹⁷ for the methane - TIP4P/2005 water interaction optimized to describe the experimental properties of methane in water.

To describe salts in water we shall use the recently developed Madrid-2019 force field⁸⁶. This force field was developed to describe ions in water as described by the TIP4P/2005 model. This new model uses the idea of scaling charges to account for the polarization of electrolytes in water. The charge assigned to the ions is reduced to $\pm 0.85 e$ in case of monovalent atoms. This model describes quite well the densities of a number of salts in solution. One may expect that a first necessary (but not sufficient) ingredient to describe the salting out effect is a correct description of the density of both, pure water and that of the salt solution. This requirement is satisfied by the Madrid-2019 force field. Let us mention that for NaCl we published in 2017 a model for NaCl that was denoted as the Madrid model⁸⁵. The Madrid model also uses the scaling of the charges with the value of $\pm 0.85 e$. Whereas in the Madrid model only properties of NaCl were considered in the target set, in the case of the Madrid-2019 the properties of a number of salts (containing either Na and/or Cl) were included in the target set. In any case for NaCl the differences between the parameters of these two models (Madrid and Madrid-2019) are rather small.

The last ingredient of the force field is a description of the interaction between methane and the ions of the system. We shall simply use LB combining rules with $\chi = 1$ for this interaction. Notice that since the amount of methane in water is small (its solubility is small) and because the number of ions in solution is also not too big, the cross interaction

between the gas and the ions does not play a key role when describing the salting out effect (at least for concentrations below 2 m).

The parameters used in this work for water and methane are collected in Table I. The force field for the salts studied here are explained in detail in the original work⁸⁶.

TABLE I. Force field parameters of the water and methane models used in this work. Water molecules are described using the TIP4P/2005 model (Ref. 13) and the LJ interaction parameters for methane are taken from Refs. 11 and 12.

Molecule	q	σ	ϵ
	e	Å	kJ/mol
TIP4P/2005			
O	0	3.1589	0.7749
H	0.5564		
M	-1.1128		
Methane			
CH ₄	0	3.7300	1.2263

Some simulations will also be performed with models that use integer charges for the ions (in electron units). In particular we shall perform simulations for the Smith-Dang²³ model of NaCl in combination with TIP4P/2005. We shall also perform simulations for the Joung and Cheatham⁶⁹ model of NaCl (set of parameters for SPC/E water) in combination with both the TIP4P/2005 and the SPC/E models of water⁵⁰. Basically we take the parameters for Na and Cl ions from the work of Smith and Dang or Joung and Cheatham and used LB combining rules to describe the interaction with TIP4P/2005 water or SPC/E water. These models will be denoted as SD-TIP4P/2005, JC-TIP4P/2005 and JC-SPC/E. Two of these force fields were used in previous works (Ref. 15, 98, and 99 for the SD-TIP4P/2005 and Ref. 85 for the JC-TIP4P/2005). We have shown recently that replacing SPC/E by TIP4P/2005 does not change much the solubility (for the JC force field it changes from 3.7 m to 3.4 m)⁸⁵. When using models with integer charges, we also used $\chi = 1.07$ for the interaction between methane and water (both for TIP4P/2005 and SPC/E).

III. SIMULATION DETAILS

To study the salting out effect we employed the direct coexistence method^{100–103}. A slab of pure water (or salty solution) will be put in contact with a slab of the pure gas along the z axis. Thus the interface will be perpendicular to the z axis. We have carried out Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations in GROMACS package^{104,105} in the Np_zT ensemble. The liquid phase will contain 6660 molecules of water (and a certain number of molecules of salt depending on the molality). The number of molecules in the gas phase will be 1000. As the solubility of methane in water is small, only a small fraction of these 1000 molecules will dissolve in water (we checked that never more than 100). Our choice for the number of molecules of water, 6660, is rather convenient since for this number, 120 molecules of salt will correspond to a molality of about 1m. We used the leap-frog integrator algorithm¹⁰⁶, and a time step of 2 fs to solve the equation of motion. Periodic boundary conditions in all directions were used. The Nosé-Hoover thermostat^{107,108} was set with a coupling constant of 2 ps to keep constant the temperature of the system. Anisotropic pressure was applied in the z direction using the Parrinello-Rahman barostat¹⁰⁹ with time constant of 2 ps. For electrostatics and van der Waals interactions the cut-off radii were fixed at 0.9 nm and long-range corrections in the energy and pressure were applied. The smooth PME method¹¹⁰ to account for the long-range electrostatic forces was used. To maintain the water geometry the LINCS algorithm^{111,112} has been applied and SHAKE¹¹³ in the case of sulfate anions. Typically the length of the runs was of about 80 ns. Four independent runs were performed for each considered state presented in this work. A snapshot of the set-up of our simulations is shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1. Configuration obtained from our Np_zT runs. Pressure is applied in the direction perpendicular to the interface (i.e along the z axis). A reservoir of molecules of methane in the gas phase (at 200 bar and 324.65 K) is in equilibrium with a salt solution of NaCl (4 m) in water. Molecules of methane dissolve into the water solution. The molality of methane in water is obtained from the density profile. Water molecules are represented as sticks in red and white colors and methane molecules as cyan spheres. The ions of the salt correspond to yellow spheres for the Cl^- and blue for Na^+ ions.

The salting out effect is quantified with the empirical Setchenow equation, which linearizes the logarithm of the ratio of the molality of the gas (methane in our case) in pure water m^0 and in salt solution, versus the salt molality, m_{salt} . This equation is expressed as:

$$\ln \left(\frac{m_{gas}^0}{m_{gas}} \right) = k_{salt} m_{salt} \quad (4)$$

where k_{salt} is the salting out coefficient of the Setchenow equation. The addition of salt provokes an exponential decrease of the molality of the gas in the aqueous solution (assuming that k_{salt} is positive).

A few words on the thermodynamics of the salting out effect is worth. The solubility of methane in pure water occurs when the chemical potential of the gas $\mu_{CH_4}(T, p, gas\ phase)$ is identical to that in solution:

$$\mu_{CH_4}(T, p, gas\ phase) = \mu_{CH_4}(T, p, solution) = \mu_{CH_4}^\dagger + kT \ln(\gamma_{CH_4}^0 m_{CH_4}^0) \quad (5)$$

where the superscript zero just reflects that no salt is present in water, $\gamma_{CH_4}^0$ and $m_{CH_4}^0$ are the activity coefficient and the molality of methane in water respectively and $\mu_{CH_4}^\dagger$ represents the Henry's law standard chemical potential of methane. When salt is added then one obtains:

$$\mu_{CH_4}(T, p, gas\ phase) = \mu(T, p, solution) = \mu_{CH_4}^\dagger + kT \ln(\gamma_{CH_4} m_{CH_4}) \quad (6)$$

by subtracting these two equations (after noticing that the chemical potential of methane in the gas phase is almost identical in both cases as the presence of the salt does not affect much the chemical potential of the methane in the gas phase) one obtains:

$$\ln(m_{CH_4}^0/m_{CH_4}) = \ln(\gamma_{CH_4}/\gamma_{CH_4}^0) \quad (7)$$

and using now Setchenow relation one obtains:

$$\ln(\gamma_{CH_4}^0) + k_{salt} m_{salt} = \ln(\gamma_{CH_4}) \quad (8)$$

According to this equation the activity coefficient of methane in water increases exponentially by the addition of salt. Thus capturing the salting out effect requires a correct description of the activity coefficient of methane in salty water. We have shown recently that scaled charges are able to describe much better the activity coefficient of NaCl in water and the change in the chemical potential of water due to the addition of salt. The salting out coefficient will inform us if the model is also able to evaluate the activity coefficient of methane in the salty solution.

IV. RESULTS

We shall now present the results of the salting out of methane obtained in this work for two types of models. The first family is formed by models in which the charge assigned to the ions is ± 1 (in electron units) as is the case of the SD-TIP4P/2005, JC-TIP4P/2005 and JC-SPC/E force fields. The second type of force fields are based on the use of scaled charges for the Na^+ and Cl^- ions as is the case of the Madrid and Madrid-2019 force fields. In Figure 2 the results for the salting out of methane in an aqueous NaCl solution at 200 bar are shown. It can be seen that the models using integer charges qualitatively predict the salting out effect (i.e, the reduction of solubility of methane when adding NaCl). We have also included

in Fig. 2 our previous results¹⁵ for the SD-TIP4P/2005 model obtained at a slightly different pressure (1 bar) and using a different approach which involved the calculation of the chemical potential of methane via the Widom test particle method. Notice that the results of this work obtained from direct coexistence runs are in acceptable agreement with the results coming from our previous work at different thermodynamic conditions (which certainly had higher statistical uncertainty).

It is clear from the data in Fig. 2 that models with unit charges overestimate significantly the magnitude of the salting out coefficient. On the other hand, models that use scaled the charges reproduce much better the experimental results^{114,115} in the range of concentrations considered. Differences between the results of the Madrid and the Madrid-2019 force field are quite small (an expected result as the parameters of the Madrid-2019 force field for NaCl are just a minor modification of those of the Madrid force field).

FIG. 2. Logarithm of the ratio of the molality of methane in pure water, $m_{\text{CH}_4}^0$, and in NaCl solutions, m_{CH_4} as a function of the molality of NaCl, m_{salt} . Results were obtained at 200 bar and 324.65 K. Solid line: experimental results¹¹⁴; filled and empty pink triangles: SD-TIP4P/2005 model as obtained in this work and as reported by Docherty *et al.*¹⁵; green diamonds: JC-TIP4P/2005 model; green empty square: JC-SPC/E; squares: Madrid force field; circles: Madrid-2019 force field.

An interesting question is the number of contact ion pairs (CIP) in the water solution for the different models. They are presented in Table II. As it can be seen the CIP is small for the Madrid-2019 and for the JC-SPC/E. They are somewhat larger for the JC-TIP4P/2005. For the SD they were already large even at a concentration of 2m. This is due to the low solubility of the model.

TABLE II. Number of contact ion pairs evaluated for NaCl solutions from the simulations of this work.

Model	m_{NaCl}	CIP
	mol/kg	
Madrid-2019	2	0.06
	4	0.11
SD-TIP4P/2005	2	?
	4	?
JC-TIP4P/2005	2	0.12
	4	0.22
JC-SPC/E	2	0.07
	4	0.15

An interesting question refers to the solvation of methane in salty solutions. For that purpose we have performed computer simulations in the NpT ensemble for a system containing methane (with the number of molecules required to reproduce the solubility at 200 bar and 324.65 K) and a 4 m NaCl solution using the Madrid-2019 force field. In Figure 3 the methane-oxygen (water), methane- Na^+ and methane- Cl^- radial distribution functions are presented. As it can be seen, methane is mostly surrounded by water. However some Cl^- anions are able to be in contact with the methane molecule though the cation Na^+ are not able to do the same. Probably the hydration of the cation is quite strong so that the contact with the molecule of methane occurs very rarely whereas the anion Cl^- has a weaker hydration shell which does not disable the access to methane.

FIG. 3. Radial distribution function between methane and the oxygen of water (OW), methane- Na^+ , and methane- Cl^- for a 4 *m* salty solution described by the Madrid-2019 force field. The number of methane molecules were chosen to reproduce the solubility of methane in the salty solution as given by the model at 200 bar and 324.6 K.

From the the radial distribution function, the coordination numbers of methane, n^A , may be calculated as

$$n^A = 4\pi\rho_A \int_0^{r_{min}} g_{\text{CH}_4-A}(r) r^2 dr, \quad (9)$$

where g_{CH_4-A} is the methane-A radial distribution function (A being either the oxygen of water, Cl^- or Na^+) and ρ_A is the number density of atoms of type A. The integral upper limit r_{min} is the position of the first minimum in the radial distribution function in the cases of oxygen and Cl^- , and the first inflection point in the case of Na^+ . The hydration number of methane in the 4 *m* solution is 18.2. The corresponding coordination number is 1.3 for Cl^- while only 0.3 Na^+ ions are in the first coordination shell of methane. Experimental reports indicate that the the hydration number of methane is 20 when no salt is present¹¹⁶, so our prediction seem to be in good agreement with experiment. Our results suggest that one of the molecules of water in the hydration shell is replaced by Cl^- in the NaCl solution.

After discussing the results for NaCl solutions we now present the results for other electrolytes. In Table III the numerical data for the salting out effect of methane in several salty solutions are collected. The predictions of the Madrid-2019 model are in good agreement with experimental data for NaCl, KCl, MgCl₂ and K₂SO₄. This is certainly satisfying as we have included divalent ions that are usually difficult to be described by common force fields. The Madrid-2019 force field overestimates slightly the salting out coefficient for CaCl₂ and MgSO₄ and underestimates it for Na₂SO₄ but the deviations are not too large.

TABLE III. Simulation results for the salting out of methane in several solutions at 200 bar and 324.65 K using the Madrid-2019 model. Experimental data come from Stoessel and Byrne.¹¹⁵ Number in parenthesis represent the estimated error from the standard deviation of four independent runs.

Salt	T (K)	p (bar)	m_{salt} (mol/kg)	m_{CH_4} (mol/kg)	$\ln \left(\frac{m_{CH_4}^o}{m_{CH_4}} \right)$	
					Sim.	Exp.
-	324.65	200	0	14.2(1)x10 ⁻²	0	0
NaCl	324.65	200	2	8.1(2)x10 ⁻²	0.56(12)	0.56
			4	5.3(6)x10 ⁻²	0.99(16)	1.11
KCl	324.65	200	2	8.7(1)x10 ⁻²	0.49(13)	0.47
MgCl ₂	324.65	200	2	5.7(1)x10 ⁻²	0.91(17)	0.87
CaCl ₂	324.65	200	2	4.3(9)x10 ⁻²	1.19(22)	0.98
Na ₂ SO ₄	324.65	200	1.5	5.2(6)x10 ⁻²	1.01(13)	1.25
K ₂ SO ₄	324.65	200	0.6	9.8(1)x10 ⁻²	0.37(08)	0.45
MgSO ₄	324.65	200	1.5	4.6(6)x10 ⁻²	1.13(20)	0.91

The capacity of the Madrid-2019 force field to describe the correct order in the salting out of several salts containing chloride is shown in Fig. 4. This is a rather difficult test to pass. The Madrid-2019 force field is able to predict correctly that the salting out coefficient of KCl solutions is lower than that of NaCl ones, when compared at the same concentration. This is in agreement with experiment. Thus for chloride salts with monovalent cations,

smaller ions provoke higher salting out. For divalent cations the opposite trend is found. In fact in this case the salting out effect of CaCl_2 is larger than that of MgCl_2 . This trend is correctly described by simulations as shown in Fig. 4. As it can be seen the model is able to capture also these subtle chemical issues. Probably the physical picture can be unified in one thinks that in the case of magnesium, the hydration is so strong that the true cation is the $\text{Mg}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ (the hydration number of Mg^{2+} is six in the Madrid-2019 force field), and this hydrated cation is certainly larger than Ca^{2+} (the strength of the hydration of Ca^{2+} is weaker than in Mg^{2+}). As it can be seen in Fig. 4 for a certain molality, the salting out of the divalent cation chloride salts is larger than this of monovalent cations. This can be explained in simple terms as 1 mole of NaCl generates 2 moles of ions, whereas 1 mole of CaCl_2 generates 3 moles of ions so that an approximate factor of $2/3$ (or $3/2$) is expected (all other factors being identical which certainly is a severe approximation).

FIG. 4. Salting out of methane as obtained from computer simulations using the Madrid-2019 model. We are showing the results of different salts having chloride as anion. The solid curve represents experimental results. The dashed line represents simulation results.

Although the main focus of this work was to analyze the salting out effect, the direct coexistence simulations performed allow to obtain some information on the interfacial properties of the gas with the salty solution. In fact the direct coexistence technique allows to compute the interfacial tension (IFT) γ as :

$$\gamma = \frac{L_z}{2}(p_{zz} - (p_{xx} + p_{yy})/2) \tag{10}$$

where as described in the Section III, z is the direction perpendicular to the interface. In Table IV the values of γ obtained from the simulations of this work are reported. It is important to point out that IFT are quite sensitive to the value of the cutoff at which the LJ part of the potential was truncated (Ewald sums in principle includes correctly the long range ionic contributions). For this reason for a rigorous determination of the value of γ one should include long range corrections to γ and there are several routes for doing that¹¹⁷. In the case of the vapor-liquid interface of pure water these long range corrections are typically of about 4-6 mJ/m² and are positive¹¹⁸. To the best of our knowledge these type of corrections have not been evaluated for a water-gas interface under pressure. One may expect similar value of the magnitude and sign for these type of interfaces. Thus the values reported in Table IV, are approximate, as the inclusion of long range correction to γ will modify then (most likely by increasing them by about 4-6 mJ/m²). Even taking this into account, we believe that there are some interesting conclusions that can be obtained from the results of this table.

TABLE IV. Interfacial tension results for methane in different salt solutions at 200 bar and 324.65 K. Simulation results obtained in this work with Madrid-2019 model. Number in parenthesis are the typical deviation for four runs.

Model	Salt	T	p	m_{salt}	γ	$\Delta\gamma$
		K	bar	mol/kg	mJ/m ²	mJ/m ²
TIP4P/2005	-	324.65	200	0	48.8(3)	0
Madrid	NaCl	324.65	200	2	51.5(4)	2.7
				4	55.9(5)	7.1
Madrid-2019	NaCl	324.65	200	2	51.8(2)	3.0
				4	55.0(4)	6.2
Madrid-2019	KCl	324.65	200	2	51.6(2)	2.8
Madrid-2019	MgCl ₂	324.65	200	2	54.0(2)	5.2
Madrid-2019	CaCl ₂	324.65	200	2	55.7(3)	6.9
Madrid-2019	Na ₂ SO ₄	324.65	200	1.5	52.5(2)	3.7
Madrid-2019	K ₂ SO ₄	324.65	200	0.6	49.9(3)	1.1
Madrid-2019	MgSO ₄	324.65	200	1.5	53.4(3)	4.6

First of all let us analyze the values of γ in the absence of salt. For methane we obtained a value of about 49 mJ/m². It is interesting to point out that the IFT for the vapor-liquid interface of pure water around 324 K is of about 61 mJ/m² for the water model considered in this work¹¹⁸ (when non including long range corrections to γ). Thus one may think, that water when having an interface with vacuum (the vapor pressure of water is very low at this temperature) has a value of γ of about 61 mJ/m², and this value reduces to about 49 mJ/m² due to the methane-water interactions at the interface.

What is the impact of adding salt to the value of γ ? As it can be seen the value of γ increases when adding salt to the aqueous solution. This effect is well known for the vapor-aqueous electrolyte solution interface, and it also holds for the aqueous electrolyte-gas interface. According to the Gibbs adsorption isotherm, the increases of γ implies that the ions do not adsorb on the surface of water (i.e they have negative adsorption). Ions do not like the surface, regardless whether in the surface, vapor or methane are waiting to

interact with them. They prefer to be solvated. When water is contact with methane the interfacial free energy increases by about 6-7 mJ/m² when adding salt to the water to form a 4 *m* solution. As to the specificity of the effect it seems that CaCl₂ is quite effective in increasing the value of γ as even a 2 *m* solution increases the value of γ by 7 mJ/m². With NaCl it is necessary to have a 4 *m* solution to see a similar increases of the value of γ . In all the cases the value of γ increased when adding salt.

In fig.5 the change in the methane-water solution IFT (at 200 bar and 324.65 K) due to the presence of NaCl is plotted as a function of the molality of the salt. Results from the simulations of this work for the Madrid-2019 model are compared to experimental results from two different works^{119,120}. Notice that the uncertainty for $\Delta\gamma$ of our work is of about 1mJ/m². As it can be seen the model describes reasonably well the experimental results (even more when considering the differences between the two experimental groups) although they tend to be slightly below the experimental ones.

FIG. 5. Change in the interfacial free energy of the methane-water interface at 200 bar and 324.65 K due to the addition of NaCl plotted as a function of the molality of the salt. Symbols experimental results taken from: Kashefi et al.¹¹⁹ (circles), Liu et al.¹²⁰ (squares). The red dashed line is a fit to the experimental results. The solid black line corresponds to the results of this work for the Madrid-2019 model.

Let us finish by presenting the density profile of water and methane along the interface. Results will be shown for the interface between pure water and methane and for the interface between a 4m NaCl aqueous solution and methane. Results were obtained using the Madrid-2019 force field at 200 bar and 324.65 K. Results are shown in Fig.6 and in fig.7. As it can be seen the methane molecule presents positive adsorption at the water-gas interface (both for pure water and for the solution). In the case of water it also presents positive adsorption when salt is added to the solution.

FIG. 6. Density profile at the water-methane interface (200 bar, 324.65K) . Results were obtained by using TIP4P/2005 for water and methane described by a single LJ site as described previously. Black solid line: Density profile of methane. Red solid line: Density profile of water.

FIG. 7. Density profile at the NaCl(4m) solution - methane interface (200 bar, 324.65 K) by using the Madrid-2019 force field. Black solid line: Density profile of methane. Red solid line: Density profile of water.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this work we have addressed the issue of the reduction of the solubility of methane in water by the addition of salt (i.e salting out effect). We have performed computer simulations to determine the salting out coefficient. The model used for water is TIP4P/2005. The methane-water interaction was tuned to reproduce the experimental value of the solubilities. For NaCl we have considered two type of force fields. The first family is that of models using unit charges for the ions. The second family is that which is the concept of charge scaling. The main conclusions of this work are as follows:

- The addition of salt provokes a reduction in the solubility of methane and this is in agreement with experiment.
- The Madrid-2019 force field is able to describe quite well the majority of the experimental results, not only for NaCl but for a number of other salts. The Madrid-2019 force field can be used to obtain interesting conclusions on the salting out effect.
- Force fields that use the concept of charge scaling predict much better the salting out effect than those that do not use this idea.
- The interfacial free energies between water and a gas under pressure (methane in our study) increases by the addition of salt.

After reading this paper, the thoughts of the reader may go as follows. If I were interested in the problem of the solubility of methane in water then probably I should use scaled charges. This problem of salting out is probably useful for Chemical Engineers, but since I am not a Chemical Engineer and I am not working on salting out, I will continue with the business as usual and I will not use scaled charges. In our opinion, the community simulating ions in water is now in a crossing point of the road. It is becoming increasingly evident that traditional non-polarizable force fields for ions are not so good^{17,45,60-65,87} (viscosities, activity coefficient, solubilities and a number of other properties that has been evaluated in the last ten years are providing evidence of that). Certainly polarizable force fields will perform better. However, the idea of introducing scaled charges offers an intermediate route. It can be cheaper than polarizable force fields and improve the performance of non-polarizable force fields at zero cost. There is no free lunch so that these models can not describe everything.

In fact the Gibbs free energy of hydration is one of the properties that can not be reproduced by models using scaled charges (although in the Appendix we will show that an approximate theoretical correction brings the results of simulations close to the experimental ones). We believe that the problem of the salting out is an interesting problem to analyze if the impact on water properties of force fields using unit charges for the ions is too large. Further work is needed on this problem and with this work we hope to attract more people of the community to this interesting problem. The salting out effect can indeed be an school to learn more on force fields of ions in water.

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VI. APPENDIX. CORRECTION TO THE HYDRATION FREE ENERGY OF MODELS WITH SCALED CHARGES.

A property that is often used when designed force fields of ions in water is the Gibbs free energy of hydration. The Gibbs free energy of hydration is defined as the change in Gibbs free energy when a mole of ions in the ideal gas at a given temperature and pressure are transfered to pure water (i.e infinite dilution) at the same temperature and pressure. Notice that some authors use a slightly different criteria as they transfer the ions at constant temperature and volume to water (with this last convention the hydration free energy correspond to the excess contribution to the chemical potential).

In general, models that use scaled charges are not able to reproduce the hydration free energies found in experiments. In fact the chemical potentials and hydration free energies of salts tend to be smaller (in absolute value) than those from experiments^{85,121}. However it is interesting to point out that Leontyev and Stuchebrukhov⁷⁵ suggested to use a theoretical

correction (denoted as ΔG_{el}) which for a 1:1 electrolyte is given by:

$$\Delta G_{el} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{\epsilon_{el}}\right) \left(\frac{q_{scaled}^2}{2R_+} + \frac{q_{scaled}^2}{2R_-}\right) \quad (11)$$

In this expression R_+ and R_- are the radius of the cation and anion respectively and ϵ_{el} is related to the electronic contribution to the dielectric constant of water ($\epsilon_{el} = 1/(q_{scaled}/e)^2$) where e is the charge of the electron. This formula is similar to the Born expression for the hydration free energy of an ion but with the dielectric constant of water replaced by the the electronic contribution to it (which has a value smaller than two). When the radius is expressed in Å the correction to the hydration free energy in kJ/mol is obtained as:

$$\Delta G_{el}/(kJ/mol) = -1387.7 \left(1 - \left(\frac{q_{scaled}}{e}\right)^2\right) \left(\frac{(q_{scaled}/e)^2}{2R_+(\text{Å})} + \frac{(q_{scaled}/e)^2}{2R_-(\text{Å})}\right) \quad (12)$$

Obviously when $q_{scaled}/e = 1$ the the value of the correction is zero. For the Madrid model of NaCl $q_{scaled} = 0.85e$ and using for the radius of the ions half of the value of σ_{Na-Na} and σ_{Cl-Cl} one obtains that the value of this correction is $\Delta G_{el} = -183$ kJ/mol. Reasonable changes in the values of the radius to be used for the cation and anion modify the value of the correction by about 20kJ/mol.

The hydration free energy of the Madrid model (at 298 K and 1 bar) is $\Delta G_{MD} = -544$ kJ/mol. This value is obtained from the standard chemical potential of the Madrid model which amounts to -596.3 kJ/mol (see Table II of Ref. 85) after adding the terms given in Eqs.(23-24) of Ref. 122 which amount to 52.7 kJ/mol. When one adds $\Delta G_{el} = -183$ kJ/mol to $\Delta G_{MD} = -544$ kJ/mol one obtains -729 kJ/mol in good agreement with the experimental result which is of about -720 kJ/mol^{123,124}. Thus although the hydration free energies of models with scaled charges can not be in agreement with experiment they can be corrected with a theoretical expression of the Born type.

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